

MIXING OF MAGMA OCEAN MATERIAL INTO THE LUNAR CRUST DURING CRUSTAL FORMATION. G. Gowman¹ and J. C. Andrews-Hanna¹, ¹Lunar and Planetary Laboratory, University of Arizona, Tucson, AZ, USA 85721 (gowmang@arizona.edu).

Introduction: Earth’s Moon offers an exceptional surface record of bombardment since the stabilization of its crust. However, the result of this extensive bombardment was near-total erasure of the Moon’s earliest surface history during crustal solidification. Surface observations, therefore, retain little evidence from this early epoch. Within the crust, however, density variations induced by various geological processes including intrusions, impacts, and physical mixing could be preserved and may be visible using gravity data.

Fig. 1: *A* Lunar topography [1]. *B* Filtered surface Bouguer anomaly. Near side is on the left; far side is on the right. Extents of major impact basins [2] are marked in *B*. Maps are in Mollweide projection centered on 90°E.

When we filter the GRAIL gravity field [3] to remove large-scale crustal thickness variations and leave only smaller-scale features which represent density anomalies within the upper crust [4, 5], we observe a pervasive texture of disorganized small-scale gravity anomalies throughout the lunar highlands (Fig. 1B). Here we explore the possibility that these gravity anomalies are a result of the excavation of magma ocean material and its mixing with the crust during the earliest stages of crustal formation.

Crust formation out of the lunar magma ocean (LMO) would have lasted 10s–100s of Myr [6, 7] at the same time as the Moon experienced its highest rate of bombardment. It is unavoidable that impactors would have punctured the still-forming crust [8], forming compositional mixtures between the crust and the excavated LMO. Today, zones of heterogeneous mixing may explain the observed perva-

sive small-scale gravity anomalies. This scenario is supported by the elevated FeO content of the lunar crust compared to the pure anorthosite (PAN) composition expected from crystallization models and the elevated concentrations of highly siderophile elements (HSEs). This process would have been cut off by the continued thickening of the crust and the declining rate of bombardment, consistent with the transition to a crust dominated by pure anorthosite at depth. Here, we test this hypothesis using a stochastic cratering and mixing model.

Gravity and compositional anomalies: We apply a high-pass cosine filter to the Bouguer gravity data over spherical harmonic degrees 60–100 (Fig. 1B) to restrict the data to anomalies which likely originate within the upper crust. We also calculate the gravity field at the surface to reduce the amplifying and attenuating effects of topography on small-scale gravity variations [4, 9]. We map these anomalies’ magnitudes and find that they are similar on the near and far sides at $\sim\pm 25$ mGal. This similarity suggests that intrusive material is unlikely to be a dominant source of density variations, given that intrusive material should reach shallower depths on the near-side leading to stronger gravity anomalies.

Previous work had favored impact-generated porosity as the source of these gravity anomalies [10]; yet the heavily cratered and high-density South Pole-Aitken basin floor shows lower-amplitude gravity variations at the same wavelengths compared to the highlands crust [4]. This suggests that impact-induced porosity is not the most likely source, and that the gravity anomalies must pre-date SPA. Early bombardment when the crust was thin could have mixed low-density crust with dense LMO material in crater ejecta to create a heterogeneous near-surface mixed layer.

This process can also explain the FeO abundances in the mixed feldspathic layer of the upper crust, which are higher than that of pure anorthosite [11]. Comparing the mean highlands FeO abundance of ~ 4.2 wt% [12] to predicted FeO abundances from models of LMO crystallization [6, 7] of ~ 12 – 14 wt% shows that up to $\sim 30\%$ of the uppermost crust may represent mixed LMO material. The presence of a layer of PAN at depth is also consistent with this process, as the thickening crust and declining bombardment would eventually limit the excavation of LMO. Given these observations, we suggest that both the gravity and compositional anomalies can be explained by mixing of LMO into the newly forming crust in the Moon’s earliest history.

Crater mixing model: To test the idea of heterogeneous mixing of LMO into the crust, we develop a simple stochastic cratering model. We use the Cra-

termaker package [13] to randomly generate craters initially based on the lunar impact flux and size distribution, then apply these craters to a crustal thickening model based on the solution to the Stefan problem. The distribution of dense ejecta is tracked using a simple three-layer model (Fig. 2), in which a magma ocean is overlain by a PAN layer, which in turn is overlain by a mixed surface layer generated by the ejecta of crust-penetrating impacts that excavate both dense LMO material and the PAN layer. We test a range of crustal thickening and bombardment scenarios, tracking the excavation and mixing of LMO into the upper crust from 4.5 Ga to 2.5 Ga (Fig. 3).

Fig. 2: Schematic of the mixing model showing craters that reach only the mixed ejecta layer (Case A), the PAN layer (Case B), and the LMO (Case C). Horizontal and vertical axes are not to scale.

From the modeled crustal thickness and LMO material concentration (assuming a density contrast of 500 kg/m^3 between PAN and LMO material), we calculate gravity anomalies (Fig. 3E) and compare them to a representative area of the lunar highlands (Fig. 3F). Preliminary results suggest that the expected flux of small craters produces insufficient mixing to explain the gravity or FeO observations. Instead, it is necessary to incorporate either distal ejecta from basin-scale impacts or an increased flux of small-to-medium craters, perhaps due to debris from the Moon-forming impact [8].

Conclusions: Small-scale Bouguer gravity anomalies reveal a pervasive texture of density anomalies throughout the lunar highlands. Based on their distribution and magnitude, these anomalies were most plausibly created by mixing lunar magma ocean material into the crust during the era of crustal formation. This study relates the lunar impactor flux and size distribution to the rate and timing of crust solidification from the LMO, tying together several major questions in lunar science. Preliminary results suggest that either distal basin forming impacts contributed to the mixed feldspathic layer, or that the impact flux in the first few million years of lunar history may have been several times higher than predicted by chronology models. These gravity and compositional anomalies serve as the only surviving evidence from the early years of lunar crust formation.

Fig. 3: Output from the mixing model, including craters with 4–300-km diameters. **A** Mixed ejecta layer thickness. **B** PAN layer concentration. **C** Modeled FeO abundance. **D** Observed FeO abundance [14], centered on 0°N , 190°E . **E** Modeled gravity anomalies. **F** Observed gravity anomalies, same area as **D**. Axes are in kilometers.

References: [1] Wiczeorek M. A. (2015), *Treatise on Geophysics*, 153–193. [2] Neumann G. A. et al. (2015), *Sci. Adv.*, 1, e1500852. [3] Goossens S. J. et al. (2020), *JGR: Planets*, 125. [4] Gowman G. & Andrews-Hanna J. C. (2026), *LPSC LVII*, Abstract #1494. [5] Gowman G. et al. (2025), *LPSC LVI*, Abstract #1563. [6] Elkins-Tanton L. T. et al. (2011), *Earth Planet. Sci. Lett.*, 304, 326–336. [7] Schmidt M. W. & Kraettli G. (2022), *JGR: Planets*, 127, e2022JE007187. [8] Perera V. et al. (2018), *JGR: Planets*, 123, 1168–1191. [9] Andrews-Hanna J. C. et al. (2018), *Icarus*, 310, 1–20. [10] Jansen J. C. et al. (2017), *Icarus*, 291, 107–123. [11] Hawke B. R. et al. (2003), *JGR: Planets*, 105, 4197–4216. [12] Jolliff B. L. et al. (2000), *JGR: Planets*, 105, 4197–4216. [13] Minton D. A. (2024), *LPSC LV*, Abstract #2462. [14] Prettyman T. H. et al. (2006), *JGR: Planets*, 111.